

Scan Metrics for People Search Based on Facial Expression and Face Detection

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Abstract

Different industries use face detection in different sectors of the company, especially in security sectors and it has a far greater impact on people's lives. However, despite its advantages, it also comes with some defects or limitations, one of which includes privacy policies and false identification based on skin color. This paper seeks to contribute to this aspect by developing a framework in the form of a window-based inference engine that uses an input image to determine the best match from a list of a thousand online collected images both in real-time and offline. Error tracking indicates that there is little margin for face identification compared to the emotion detected on the face, and further improvement would be to determine and compare performance in the search and tracking processes.

Keywords: Multi-tasking convolutional neural network, Face detection, Emotion recognition, Deep learning algorithms, Inference engine, Window based convolutional neural network.

1 Introduction

The major concerns about the ubiquity of face detection systems are amplified by evidence of racial profiling and a least of protester identification, which have caused a major moratorium in companies like Microsoft, Amazon, and IBM in selling designed face detection software to law enforcement. Now as the moratoriums exceed their time limit and the technology face detection gets even

better and more affordable, society depending on its impact will need to determine answers to questions like how can facial detection systems regulate processes and how can privacy sacrifices and services be utilised in modern terms? Some of the facial detectors used in industries like movie sets have not been depicted correctly and every face detection tool must work distinctly. This can be sorted out into three (3) different basic forms:

Detection (finding a face in an image), Attribution (analyse the database by mapping faces and measuring distances), and Recognition (confirming the identity of a person in the database). The detection phase starts with an algorithm that learns the patterns in the face based on eyes, nose, and mouth features, this is done by training the photos of the faces. Cramming in enough pictures to train the model makes learn the distinct patterns in identification and makes an artificial intelligence (AI) tool. The different photos fed as input to the system have a profound differential effect on its accuracy in the module for the analysis and identification stage. Different techniques can be employed to perform the training but the best can serve as the most advanced and contributing factor to the design of AI. This paper uses a multi-tasking window-based convolutional neural network to train a list of faces in a database based on constrained and singled layered pattern search, a form customised method to increase speed and rapid identification. The proceeding sections discuss the literature on face recognition and detection and the methods adopted for this approach.

2 Literature Review

Recent research [22, 6, 18, 1] has worked on the diversity of photos fed into a system, which has a profound effect on the accuracy of the model during the analysis and recognition steps. If a sample set includes mostly white men in the first stage of facial recognition training, the procedure normally struggles to attain accuracy in BIPOC faces and women. The best method applied can correct some of these struggles, which are not been applied in the most current research, but white-faced males are still falsely detected less frequently than in a group. Misidentification is also detected in Black and Asian groups more than in white. In research by [Mutale Nkonde], some notifications were observed that some systems that are perfectly in operation can develop issues with gender identification which are typically binary with labels for male and female. And this is no way for a system like that to operate in a non-binary way for somebody who has transitioned.

Some facial recognition systems [11, 17, 19, 15, 12, 8, 10, 2, 9, 21] in law enforcement agencies can be inaccessible and the algorithms that support the detection and identification are often a black box that researchers can have access to i. If the public doesn't know how the techniques are been handled and how accurate they are, then they cannot determine whether the systems are accurate or appropriately used, especially in law enforcement. Having access to system support can help the public to be comfortable with face recognition systems and identification and choices to retrieve their information if they want to [16, 14, 23, 24, 5, 20, 7, 4, 3, 13].

3 Method

The proposed model uses multi-task CNN-based soft and hard parameters; a combination of facial features, emotion recognition, and face detection based on shared and constrained layers. The database of images collected from online and real-time photos of people involved in activities induces a happy expression rather sad or stressful expression. Some of the tasks were simply to ask them to smile or look into the camera and the default expression on the faces is rendered static. The expression on the faces is into two classes, happy or smile and neutral or sad mood. This is based on these classes because the pilot stage is to test for the best performance from these two classes in terms of emotion recognition. The databases of an image are faces trained in a single input image and the data model is then used to identify and input the image. The index page (Figure 1), is used to input the details of the person we want to search for in terms of name, color, and phone number.

These are the soft parameters, the names can match any given name with similarity to the first for letters, the identified group of similar names is displayed and the emotion on each face can be captured depending on the class of the emotion the facial expression falls in. Facial expression is also a way to determine the best match for a person. For example, a distinct attribute of a person's facial features could be the smile of the person rather than the eyes, nose, or mouth formation. These attributes serve as the hard parameters which are usually called during the search loop.

Figure 1: Index page for the input of the name of a person to search for in the database of different faces.

4 Result

Figure 1 shows the index for input search and Figure 2 shows a list of images that have similarities in terms of the first few letters in the name of entries on the index page, color might be a perfect parameter to identify a face best it is also a criterion to produce the best match. Due to the bias in color features of an image, the color of a person is not set as one of the important features to search for a person and hence can be listed as an attribute

that can contribute significantly to the performance of the model. The best feature listed for the best match is the expression on the face of the person captured at the initial stage of the data collection. The characterisation of features of the face is based on three (3) main attributes, the shape of the eyes, nose, and mouth. An acyclic rendered is used to cascade these regions for each face and produce a different color outline for each face since every face must have a different expression during the initial image capture.

The deep learning approach for CNN in Matlab is equipped with rendering and cascaded abilities that can perfectly capture and render the selected region of the soft parameters (eyes, nose, and mouth), each circle interests the centroid of the face which is the middle of the nose. Research has confirmed that emotions such as grief are mostly similar to gloomy countenance, and there is also characteristic facial expression which is observed to be similar to anger and excitement. CNN can be used to distinguish each of these expressions with a different mapping that can give the best interpretation of any face. Though facial emotion data are more difficult to control they are most utilised in areas like user experience that exceed what users are able or willing to disclose to an evaluator without subject views.

Figure 3 shows detected faces with different facial expressions that are related to smile, happy, and neutral faces. The expression on the face is a unique and distinct attribute that identifies a person. There is a high agreement for neural, happy, and smiling emotions, less for sad, angry, and stressful emotions since the images were a majority of random images collected from either induced emotion simply by looking into the camera. The model detects the presence of a face, and then the faces are modelled using the multi-task CNN algorithm based on a database of the images collected with more than six hundred expressions and key points in the faces. The algorithm can also detect the position of aspects of the face, such as important features like the eyes, nose, and mouth open or closed, and the nature and structure of the brows either raised or lowered. The captured faces were mostly seen interacting with products they liked or simply looking into the camera. All captured images are rendered static. This also has its limitations, such as emotions can occur without facial expressions and facial expressions can also occur without emotions. People may also experience emotions that are totally different and thus the algorithm may not record or match the accurate reading of a person's face.

The system also allows for a re-run in such a case for other objects and different color effects, one part is based on multiple searches on the emotion detected on the face to recognise the face in addition to its basic features, while the other is based on the detected static face with arbitrary features. Figure 4 shows a different output of detected faces and features of the face with different color

outputs based on simple face identification rather than mood selection.

The best attribute here is simply the presence of eyes, mouth, and nose, other added attributes such as the expression on the face are called in within the loop at a distinct time interval depending on the pattern of search. The face detection tool is also capable of displaying the probability that the person is expressing specific emotions, it can be modified to interpret that a person is experiencing certain emotions with a combination of other detected emotions depending on the angle of the face and primary mood of the person. This procedure is extremely valuable when one is dealing with products that the person may not be comfortable discussing in real time – the facial detection tool can tell evaluators what emotions users experience that can then represent a cascade of fixation points on a product webpage in a user experience study.

Figure 5 shows a detected face from the search criteria of a person named “Sarah, Black”, with a black color attribute, the search came up with the exact match with a 0.99% and a record smiling emotion from MTCNN search, the rendering captured all features of the face and maps the exact features to the person identified with the exact soft parameters. The proceeding Figures briefly discuss errors in both the emotion recognition and face detected tasks.

Figure 6a shows five different test runs on five epochs (2, 4, 3, 6, and 5) as the number of hidden layers for the MTCNN model. The error detected is seen to fall on the same level, which means any of the epochs can be used for pattern search the least error is at 0.2%, which gives a maximum performance of 80% at the third epoch

Figure 6b shows the performance in terms of error computed for the face detection task on five different epochs, least error in the third epoch such as the above for emotion recognition; this shows similar patterns in the detection of a person from a list of database and that either task can be used to determine the similarities in facial features regardless of whether the features are based on mood or basic characteristics features of the face. Real-time person detection might give a different view of people and face detection and will give a distinct view to the face recognition system. Such a report will be reserved for a future perspective.

5 Conclusion

This paper set out to investigate pattern matching based on scan metrics for people search and face detection, which employs the multi-tasking CNN that uses an input image to search for its identified form based on a trained list of databases of images. The task is based on face detection and emotion recognition that captures the basic features of the face and the initial stage for face detection and other distinct features such as the ex-

Figure 2: Sample list of images in the database, which has similar attributes to the input images.

Figure 3: List of detected facial images with different emotions identified on the faces, each representing a distinct attribute to each person.

pression on the face is called in and used as added hard parameters to determine the best match. The algorithm is trained and tested for error on each task and the least error is seen from the face detection task with an epoch of three (3). The result also shows that either attribute task can be used for face recognition and surveillance or a user experience system to identify a person and their expression in terms of what they are involved with. The future rule of the system would be to develop a model that uses deep learning algorithms to identify multiple persons as a form of parallel computing in both facial

and emotion recognition with added demographic characteristics as the distinct features of the person. This would require more facial feature points of the face as soft parameters.

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Figure 4: Different mode searches in random search can produce a different mood of the faces as another color with the same distinct expression.

Figure 5: Sample input image identified with 0.99% similarity and a classified simile emotion.

References

- [1] Zahra Amiri, Arash Heidari, Nima Jafari Navimipour, Mehmet Unal, and Ali Mousavi. Adventures in data analysis: A systematic review of deep learning techniques for pattern recognition in cyber-physical-social systems. *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, 83(8):22909–22973, 2024.
- [2] Justice Kwame Appati, Huzaiifa Abu, Ebenezer Owusu, and Kwaku Darkwah. Analysis and implementation of optimization techniques for facial recognition. *Applied Computational Intelligence and Soft Computing*, 2021(1):6672578, 2021.
- [3] Marian Stewart Bartlett, Javier R Movellan, and Terrence J Sejnowski. Face recognition by independent component analysis. *IEEE Transactions on neural networks*, 13(6):1450–1464, 2002.
- [4] F Battaglia, G Iannizzotto, and L Lo Bello. A biometric authentication system based on face recognition and rfid tags. *Mondo Digitale*, 13(49):340–346, 2014.
- [5] Rama Chellappa, Charles L Wilson, and Saad Sirohey. Human and machine recognition of faces: A survey. *Proceedings of the IEEE*, 83(5):705–741, 1995.
- [6] Jeffrey Donahue, Lisa Anne Hendricks, Sergio Guadarrama, Marcus Rohrbach, Subhashini Venugopalan, Kate Saenko, and Trevor Darrell. Long-term recurrent convolutional networks for visual recognition and description. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 2625–2634, 2015.
- [7] Mika Fischer, Hazim Kemal Ekenel, and Rainer Stiefelwagen. Person re-identification in tv series using robust face recognition and user feedback. *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, 55:83–104, 2011.
- [8] Pete Fussey, Bethan Davies, and Martin Innes. ‘assisted’ facial recognition and the reinvention of sus-

(a) Computed error for emotion recognition task on five different epochs.

(b) Error in performance using face detection on five different epochs of MTCNN

Figure 6: Performance based on error computation for aggregate detected faces.

picion and discretion in digital policing. *The British journal of criminology*, 61(2):325–344, 2021.

- [9] Javier Galbally, Pasquale Ferrara, Rudolf Haraksim, Apostolos Psyllos, Laurent Beslay, et al. Study on face identification technology for its implementation in the schengen information system. *Publications Office of the European Union*, 2019.
- [10] Siem Girmay, Faniel Samsom, and Asad Masood Khattak. Ai based login system using facial recognition. In *2021 5th Cyber Security in Networking Conference (CSNet)*, pages 107–109. IEEE, 2021.
- [11] Patrick J Grother, Patrick J Grother, P Jonathon Phillips, and George W Quinn. *Report on the evaluation of 2D still-image face recognition algorithms*. US Department of Commerce, National Institute of Standards and Technology, 2011.
- [12] S Harinee and M Vijay Anand. Digital solutions for crime control: A comprehensive criminal identification and reporting framework. In *2024 11th International Conference on Reliability, Infocom Technologies and Optimization (Trends and Future Directions)(ICRITO)*, pages 1–6. IEEE, 2024.
- [13] Xiaofei He, Shuicheng Yan, Yuxiao Hu, Partha Niyogi, and Hong-Jiang Zhang. Face recognition using laplacianfaces. *IEEE transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence*, 27(3):328–340, 2005.
- [14] Gary B Huang, Marwan Mattar, Tamara Berg, and Eric Learned-Miller. Labeled faces in the wild: A database for studying face recognition in unconstrained environments. In *Workshop on faces in Real-Life Images: detection, alignment, and recognition*, 2008.
- [15] Lucas Introna and David Wood. Picturing algorithmic surveillance: The politics of facial recognition systems. *Surveillance & Society*, 2(2/3):177–198, 2004.
- [16] Anil K Jain, Arun Ross, and Salil Prabhakar. An introduction to biometric recognition. *IEEE Transactions on circuits and systems for video technology*, 14(1):4–20, 2004.
- [17] Thaddeus L Johnson, Natasha N Johnson, Denise McCurdy, and Michael S Olajide. Facial recognition systems in policing and racial disparities in arrests. *Government Information Quarterly*, 39(4):101753, 2022.
- [18] Jongyoo Kim, Hui Zeng, Deepti Ghadiyaram, Sanghoon Lee, Lei Zhang, and Alan C Bovik. Deep convolutional neural models for picture-quality prediction: Challenges and solutions to data-driven image quality assessment. *IEEE Signal processing magazine*, 34(6):130–141, 2017.
- [19] Rely Victoria Petrescu. Face recognition as a biometric application. *Journal of Mechatronics and Robotics*, 3:237–257, 2019.

- [20] P Jonathon Phillips, Hyeonjoon Moon, Syed A Rizvi, and Patrick J Rauss. The feret evaluation methodology for face-recognition algorithms. *IEEE Transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence*, 22(10):1090–1104, 2000.
- [21] Andrew Jason Shepley. Deep learning for face recognition: a critical analysis. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1907.12739*, 2019.
- [22] Antonio Torralba, Rob Fergus, and William T Freeman. 80 million tiny images: A large data set for nonparametric object and scene recognition. *IEEE transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence*, 30(11):1958–1970, 2008.
- [23] Matthew A Turk and Alex P Pentland. Face recognition using eigenfaces. In *Proceedings. 1991 IEEE computer society conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 586–587. IEEE Computer Society, 1991.
- [24] Wenyi Zhao, Rama Chellappa, P Jonathon Phillips, and Azriel Rosenfeld. Face recognition: A literature survey. *ACM computing surveys (CSUR)*, 35(4):399–458, 2003.